

GnIOWA Operators and Some Weights Allocation Methods with Their Properties

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Abstract

This study proposes some standard and general forms of induced ordered weighted averaging (GnIOWA) operators where the inductive information is ordered weighted averaging (OWA) weight vectors instead of real numbers. It shows the usefulness of

such type of generalized induced OWA in decision-making and evaluation and many other applications. We propose three weights allocation methods that are specifically designed for the proposed GnIOWA operators. For each of the proposed weights allocation methods, a numerical example is also attached accordingly. With the use of convex/concave Regular Increasing Monotone quantifiers, we further discuss some mathematical properties of these weights allocation methods.

Keywords: aggregation operators, decision making, IOWA operators, OWA operators, preference-involved aggregation

1 Introduction

Aggregation operators (also known as aggregation functions) are very powerful in a myriad of evaluation problems, from which decision makers can further appraise some certain objects under evaluation and afterwards take corresponding decisions, such as choosing the best few ones. The studies of aggregation operators have been witnessing a continuous development for the past decades both in theoretical and application areas [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Given input information, for example, representing several scores from different criteria for evaluating one certain object, an aggregation operator serves as a reasonable tool to merge them into a single value as the final aggregation result, significantly facilitating the decision-making and evaluation processes [20, 21, 22, 23].

Given input information which is represented as a vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in [0, 1]^n$, an aggregation operator F always deals with them by producing a single output $F(\mathbf{x}) \in [0, 1]$. Generally speaking, aggregation operators can be classified into subcategories according to different perspectives. One classification is from characteristics of the resulting values, dividing aggregation operators into subcategories according to which range of $[0, \text{Min}(\mathbf{x})]$, $[\text{Min}(\mathbf{x}), \text{Max}(\mathbf{x})]$, and $[\text{Max}(\mathbf{x}), 1]$ the resulting value $F(\mathbf{x})$ will fall into. If an aggregation operator always returns a value $F(\mathbf{x}) \in [\text{Min}(\mathbf{x}), \text{Max}(\mathbf{x})]$, then F is called an *averaging operator* [1]. For example, the commonly known arithmetic mean, median, Weighted Averaging (WA), max, min, geometrical mean, and so forth, all of which belong to averaging function.

Another classification is from the angle of whether or not there are some specified preferences (such as bipolar preferences) on the aggregation operators and over the aggregation processes. If an aggregation operator is assigned a given preference expressed by a weight vector or a capacity, then it can be regarded as a type of *preference-involved aggregation operators*. The aggregation results will be essentially affected by those preferences exerted. For example, WA operator, Ordered Weighted Averaging (OWA) operator [24], Induced Ordered Weighted Averaging (IOWA) operator [25, 26], Choquet Integral [27], Sugeno Integral [28], and Shilkret Integral [29] are all different cases of preference-involved aggregation operators.

Among the foregoing preference-involved aggregation operators, the OWA operators [24] feature on the pre-assigned (bipolar) weight vectors which can effectively embody the optimism/pessimism bipolar preferences of decision makers. In addition, the extent of these preferences can be also measured by orness/andness degree [24, 30] of those weight vectors attached to them. The Choquet Integrals assigned with some given capacities are also an important type of averaging operator, and they proved to be a generalization of both WA and OWA operators with specific capacities [27]. Besides, the attached capacities to Choquet Integrals are some more complex than bipolar preferences, and they are more difficult to generate.

The weight vector (also known as OWA weight vector) assigned to OWA operators is a deciding factor to related aggregation results. Once each input value is assigned with a weight, then the remaining processes in OWA and IOWA aggregation become the same to WA. The weights allocation methods are distinctly different in OWA and IOWA operators. Simply speaking, in OWA aggregation, an input value is assigned with a weight according to its magnitude, while in IOWA aggregation, an input value is allocated with a weight according to another inductive value attached to it. That attached inductive value decides the weights allocation in IOWA aggregation, and therefore when the inductive values are selected to be just input values themselves, IOWA aggregation essentially or practically degenerates into OWA aggregation.

Both the input values and their attached inductive values can have practical meanings in real applications. For example, an input vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ can represent scores and an inductive vector $\mathbf{t} = (t_1, \dots, t_n)$ can be the date when those scores achieved. However, with the fast development of information technique, in ever-increasingly more decision-making problems the information we face and need to aggregate is more complex than real values.

The complex information can be used for direct aggregation as in WA and OWA aggregation, and it can also be used as inductive information for assigning weights to corresponding input values as in IOWA aggregation. Clearly, the weight allocation based on complex information will be more complicated than those commonly adopted in OWA and IOWA aggregation. When the complex information becomes some OWA weight vectors, they have also witnessed numerous applications involving those OWA weight vectors, in which they are also known as some other terminologies, such as subjective probability vector and preference vectors [6]. The main aim of this study is to devise some reasonable weights allocation methods when the inductive information becomes OWA weight vectors. With such analyses, we will then formally define the general forms of induced ordered weighted averaging (GnIOWA) with inductive information being preference vectors (or OWA weight vectors). There is a paucity of approaches to performing induced aggregation where the inducing variable can be modeled by OWA weight vectors or probability vectors. This study proposes some different inducing weighting methods in the environ-

ment where inducing variables are vectors, and thus it is meaningful in both aggregation theory and decision-making practices.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 rephrases aggregation functions, OWA operators, and IOWA operators using some strict languages. Section 3 introduces a general form of IOWA operators induced by OWA weight vectors with some applications. In Section 4, we propose two weights allocation methods for IOWA operators considering the structures of accumulation vectors. Section 5 discusses another weights allocation method for IOWA operators induced from the structures of OWA weight vectors. In Section 6, based on convex/concave Regular Increasing Monotone (RIM) quantifiers, we discuss some mathematical properties of the three weights inductive methods. Section 7 recaps and concludes this study.

2 Some Reviews and Discussions about Aggregation Functions, OWA Operators, and IOWA Operators

In this study, a sequence form $\mathbf{x} = (x_i)_{i=1}^n$ and a vector form $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ of the input for aggregation are regarded as equivalent and will be interchangeably used throughout. The space of all such sequences/vectors is conventionally denoted by $[0, 1]^n$. An n -dimensional normalized weight vector used for aggregation is also denoted by either sequence form $\mathbf{w} = (w_i)_{i=1}^n$ or by vector form $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_n)$, interchangeably. Besides, the space of all such weight sequences/vectors with dimension n is denoted by $\langle n \rangle$. Furthermore, a vector formed by m weight vectors of dimension n is consistently expressed either by $W = (\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_m)$ or by sequence form $W = (\mathbf{w}_j)_{j=1}^m$, and the space of all such vectors is analogously denoted by $(\langle n \rangle)^m$. In addition, we say $\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{y}$ if and only if $x_i \leq y_i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$; we write $\mathbf{x} < \mathbf{y}$ if and only if $x_i \leq y_i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and there exist some $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $x_k < y_k$.

Since this study is only concerned with the type of averaging operator, in the next we only briefly review the concepts of averaging function in a self-contained definition.

Definition 2.1 (Averaging operator [1]). An averaging operator (of dimension n) $F: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a mapping satisfying the two conditions below:

- (i) $\text{Min}(\mathbf{x}) \leq F(\mathbf{x}) \leq \text{Max}(\mathbf{x})$;
- (ii) for any $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in [0, 1]^n$, if $\mathbf{x} < \mathbf{y}$, then $F(\mathbf{x}) \leq F(\mathbf{y})$.

Definition 2.2 (WA operator [1]). A WA operator (of dimension n) with weight vector $\mathbf{w} \in \langle n \rangle$ is an averaging operator $\text{WA}_{\mathbf{w}}: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{WA}_{\mathbf{w}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot x_i. \quad (1)$$

Definition 2.3 (OWA operator [24]). An OWA operator (of dimension n) with (OWA) weight vector $\mathbf{w} \in \langle n \rangle$ is an averaging operator $\text{OWA}_{\mathbf{w}}: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$, with

$$\text{OWA}_{\mathbf{w}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot x_{\sigma(i)}, \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ is any appropriate permutation on $\{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $x_{\sigma(i)} \geq x_{\sigma(j)}$ whenever $i < j$.

Definition 2.4 (Orness/andness [24]). The orness of any weight vector $\mathbf{w} \in \langle n \rangle$ used in OWA aggregation is defined as a mapping $\text{orness}: \langle n \rangle \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{orness}(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n-i}{n-1} \cdot w_i. \quad (3)$$

Dually, the andness of any weight vector $\mathbf{w} \in \langle n \rangle$ is defined as a function $\text{andness}: \langle n \rangle \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{andness}(\mathbf{w}) = 1 - \text{orness}(\mathbf{w}). \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.5 (RIM quantifier [32]). A function $Q: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called an RIM quantifier if Q satisfies $Q(0) = 0$, $Q(1) = 1$, and $Q(a) \geq Q(b)$ whenever $a > b$. We also denote by \mathcal{Q} the space of all RIM quantifiers.

Definition 2.6 (Q -generated OWA weight vector [32]). Given an RIM quantifier $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$, an OWA weight vector $\mathbf{w}^{(Q)} = (w_i^{(Q)})_{i=1}^n \in \langle n \rangle$ is called the Q -generated OWA weight vector (of dimension n) if it satisfies for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$,

$$w_i^{(Q)} = Q\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{i-1}{n}\right). \quad (5)$$

Definition 2.7 (Orness of RIM quantifier [32]). The orness of any RIM quantifier Q is defined by $\text{orness}: \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{orness}(Q) = \int_0^1 Q(y) dy. \quad (6)$$

Dually, the andness of any RIM quantifier Q can be defined by $\text{andness}: \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{andness}(Q) = 1 - \text{orness}(Q) = 1 - \int_0^1 Q(y) dy. \quad (7)$$

The following deduction from the case of OWA weight vector yields a strict orness definition for RIM quantifiers [32, 33]:

$$\text{orness}(Q) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n-i}{n-1} [Q\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{i-1}{n}\right)] = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} Q\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) = \int_0^1 Q(y) dy. \quad (8)$$

Moreover, if Q is absolutely continuous, then there exists a normalized density function $q: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ such that $Q(y) = \int_0^y q(t) dt$ and $\int_0^1 q(t) dt = 1$. Therefore, in such a situation (5) can be also equivalently expressed as

$$w_i^{(Q)} = Q\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{i-1}{n}\right) = \int_{(i-1)/n}^{i/n} q(t) dt. \quad (9)$$

IOWA was introduced by Yager [25, 26]; in the sequel, we review and rephrase it using a strict and convenient way proposed in recent literature [34], by which there is no need to use any permutations.

Definition 2.8 (IOWA input). An IOWA input with attached inductive information (hereinafter IOWA input) is expressed by a pair $(x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, in which x is the input for actual aggregation whereas t is the inductive information for conducting the weights allocation. A vector of IOWA inputs of dimension n is denoted as $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{t}) = ((x_i)_{i=1}^n, (t_i)_{i=1}^n)$ where \mathbf{x} is the input vector for aggregation whereas \mathbf{t} is the inductive vector attached to \mathbf{x} . The space of all vectors of IOWA inputs of dimension n is denoted by $[0, 1]^n \times [0, 1]^n$.

Definition 2.9 (IOWA operator [25, 26]). An IOWA operator (of dimension n) under RIM quantifier $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$, is an averaging operator $\text{IOWA}_Q: [0, 1]^n \times [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{IOWA}_Q(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{t}) = \text{WA}_{\mathbf{w}^{(\mathbf{t}; Q)}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^{(\mathbf{t}; Q)} \cdot x_i. \quad (10)$$

Let us define three set-valued functions $U: [0, 1]^n \times \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow 2^{\{1, \dots, n\}}$, $E: [0, 1]^n \times \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow 2^{\{1, \dots, n\}}$, and $L: [0, 1]^n \times \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow 2^{\{1, \dots, n\}}$ as

$$U(\mathbf{t}, i) = \{k : t_i < t_k\}, \quad E(\mathbf{t}, i) = \{k : t_i = t_k\}, \quad L(\mathbf{t}, i) = \{k : t_k < t_i\},$$

and define a weight vector $\mathbf{w}^{(\mathbf{t}; Q)} = \{w_i^{(\mathbf{t}; Q)}\}_{i=1}^n$ such that

$$w_i^{(\mathbf{t}; Q)} = \frac{Q\left(1 - \frac{\text{card}(U(\mathbf{t}, i))}{n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\text{card}(U(\mathbf{t}, i))}{n}\right)}{\text{card}(E(\mathbf{t}, i))}, \quad (11)$$

in which $\text{card}(\cdot)$ represents the cardinality of any finite set.

Remark 2.1. In Definition 2.9, when inductive vector \mathbf{t} is equal to input vector \mathbf{x} , then $\text{IOWA}_Q(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{t}) = \text{OWA}_{\mathbf{w}^{(Q)}}(\mathbf{x})$ where $\mathbf{w}^{(Q)}$ is defined by Definition 2.6 and Equation (5).

3 A General Form for IOWA Operators Induced by OWA Weight Vectors with Some Applications

In this section, as a motivated application, we introduce a practical evaluation problem in which a weight allocation is necessary and need to be induced by OWA weight vectors.

Suppose some objects are under evaluation and decision makers will select some better ones from them according to a comprehensive evaluation over them. The evaluation is based on n different criteria $\{C_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and we need to decide the relative importances between them by assigning different weights $(w_i)_{i=1}^n$ to them.

Below we first discuss the weights allocation method induced by real values as used in IOWA operators. For this scenario, suppose a simple survey or statistic is carried out over a given group of experts $\{E_k\}$, and each expert E_k is required to tell on his/her own opinion whether or not the criterion C_i is important for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Let $\mathbf{t} = (t_1, \dots, t_n)$ be a resulting opinion vector indicating that $100t_i\%$ of those experts think criterion C_i is important. Conforming to intuition, a larger t_i should carry more weight to C_i ; thus, some special RIM quantifier Q with $\text{orness}(Q) \geq 0.5$ appears to be the reasonable choices to help generate OWA weight vector $\mathbf{w}^{(Q)}$ for induced aggregation.

However, this common induced method based on real inductive vector sometimes may lose much more flexibilities and diversities in decision making. For example, in the aforementioned decision-making case, suppose this time there is an evaluation scale for each criterion determined based on a specified linearly ordered adverbs $\{1 \text{ "very important," } 2 \text{ "important," } 3 \text{ "less important," } 4 \text{ "not important"}\}$ (which is also equivalently represented by a linearly ordered set $(S, \leq) = (\{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \leq)$). For criterion C_i , let the opinion vector be represented by an OWA weight vector $\mathbf{t}_i = (t_{i1}, t_{i2}, t_{i3}, t_{i4})$ indicating $100t_{i1}\%$ of the experts think criterion C_i is "very important," $100t_{i2}\%$ think criterion C_i is "important," $100t_{i3}\%$ think criterion C_i is "less important," and $100t_{i4}\%$ think criterion C_i is "not important."

Since a better opinion vector for criterion C_i should cause more weight to be allocated to C_i , we need to first define a method to compare any two opinion vectors. The ordering in the lattice structure for OWA weight vectors $(\langle n \rangle, \preceq)$ provides an ideal way for such comparison. In the next we review the corresponding definition for lattice of OWA weight vectors.

Definition 3.1 (Accumulation vector of OWA weight vector [7]). For any $\mathbf{w} = (w_i)_{i=1}^n \in \langle n \rangle$, define its accumulation vector $\vec{\mathbf{w}} = (\vec{w}_i)_{i=1}^n \in [0, 1]^n$ such that $\vec{w}_i = \sum_{k=1}^i w_k$.

Definition 3.2 (Lattice of OWA weight vectors [7]). Let $\langle n \rangle$ be the space of OWA weight vectors of dimension n ; then the *lattice of OWA weight vectors* $(\langle n \rangle, \preceq)$ is defined with the precedence relation " \preceq " such that for any two OWA weight vectors $\mathbf{w}_1 = (w_{1i})_{i=1}^n \in \langle n \rangle$ and $\mathbf{w}_2 = (w_{2i})_{i=1}^n \in \langle n \rangle$, $\mathbf{w}_1 \preceq \mathbf{w}_2$ if and only if $\vec{w}_{1i} \leq \vec{w}_{2i}$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Moreover, with convention we write $\mathbf{w}_1 \prec \mathbf{w}_2$ if and only if

- (i) $\vec{w}_{1i} \leq \vec{w}_{2i}$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$,
- (ii) there exist some $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $\vec{w}_{1k} < \vec{w}_{2k}$.

In terms of the weight allocation problem depending on \mathbf{t}_i , with the precedence relation “ \preceq ,” we reckon that it will be reasonable that if $\mathbf{t}_i \preceq \mathbf{t}_j$, then C_i should be assigned less weight than C_j . On the basis of this rule, we will later discuss some different weight allocation mechanisms. In the following, we first formulate a paradigm for generalized IOWA operators by which the weight allocated should consider any given inductive information.

Definition 3.3 (General form for IOWA operators induced by OWA weight vectors). Let $\langle m \rangle$ be the space of OWA weight vectors of dimension m ($m \geq 2$), a general form for an IOWA operator (GnIOWA) (of dimension n) induced by OWA weight vectors (of dimension m) under RIM quantifier $Q \in \mathcal{Q}$, is an averaging operator $\text{GnIOWA}_{\mathbf{w}^\Delta}: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\text{GnIOWA}_{\mathbf{w}^\Delta}(\mathbf{x}) = \text{WA}_{\mathbf{w}^\Delta}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^\Delta \cdot x_i, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = H(T; Q)$ is defined as a normalized weight vector decided by a function

$$H: (\langle m \rangle)^n \times \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow [0, 1]^n \quad (13)$$

with inductive information $T = (\mathbf{t}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$ and RIM quantifier Q .

Using the general form, in the next we discuss some simple cases of IOWA operators which are induced by some indexes generated from accumulation vectors. For an OWA weight vector $\mathbf{w} \in \langle m \rangle$, there exist several indexes or measurements for it devised by scholars based on different special or practical purposes. For example, the orness of it defined in Definition 2.4 is a representative one.

Suppose we have inductive information $T = (\mathbf{t}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$ and RIM quantifier Q ; then we can easily determine $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = H(T; Q)$ by orness of each $\mathbf{t}_i = (t_{ij})_{j=1}^m$; that is, we use the weight vector determined by (11) with $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = \mathbf{w}^{\langle \mathbf{t}; Q \rangle}$ such that $\mathbf{t} = (\text{orness}(\mathbf{t}_i))_{i=1}^n$. As an alternative index, we may also choose to use $\mathbf{t} = (t_{i1})_{i=1}^n$ as the inductive vector, representing a strict judgment style by which we only consider the statistic situations of the largest scale in the evaluation scales. By extension, we can also consider the weighted forms of those evaluation scales with $\mathbf{t} = (\sum_{j=1}^m r_j t_{ij})_{i=1}^n$ where $\mathbf{r} = (r_j)_{j=1}^m$ is a normalized weight vector.

4 Weights Allocations in IOWA Operators Induced from the Structures of Accumulation Vectors

In Section 3, we formally formulated a general form for IOWA operators induced by OWA weight vectors in Definition 3.3. As some specializations, in this section, we present and discuss two different induced methods for weights allocation based on the structures of accumulation vectors of OWA weight vectors. Revolving around inductive information

$T = (\mathbf{t}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$, we will focus on the constructing of $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = (w_i^\Delta)_{i=1}^n = H(T; Q)$. The basic principle for the above two methods is based on the reasonability that the bigger entries in accumulation vector $\vec{\mathbf{t}}_i$ will help make w_i^Δ larger, and vice versa.

4.1 Weights Allocation Method 1

Entries induced weights allocation method with derived ordering from inductive information.

Step 1. For each $\mathbf{t}_i = (t_{ij})_{j=1}^m$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$), directly obtain its accumulation vector $\vec{\mathbf{t}}_i = (\vec{t}_{ij})_{j=1}^m$ by Definition 3.1, and also form the accumulation information $\vec{T} = (\vec{\mathbf{t}}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((\vec{t}_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$.

Step 2. Define three set-valued functions

$$\begin{aligned} U(T, i, j) &= \{(k, s) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m-1\} : \vec{t}_{ij} < \vec{t}_{ks}\}, \\ E(T, i, j) &= \{(k, s) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m-1\} : \vec{t}_{ij} = \vec{t}_{ks}\}, \\ L(T, i, j) &= \{(k, s) \in \{1, \dots, n\} \times \{1, \dots, m-1\} : \vec{t}_{ks} < \vec{t}_{ij}\}. \end{aligned}$$

The cardinalities of all these sets can be obtained accordingly.

Step 3. With selected RIM quantifier Q , define weight vector $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = (w_i^\Delta)_{i=1}^n = H(T; Q)$ such that

$$w_i^\Delta = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} Q\left(1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, i, j))}{(m-1)n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\text{card}(U(T, i, j))}{(m-1)n}\right)}{\text{card}(E(T, i, j))}. \quad (14)$$

Remark 4.1. Using above Method 1, when $m = 2$, it is apparent to observe that the GniOWA operator in Equation (12) $\text{GniOWA}_{\mathbf{w}^\Delta}(\mathbf{x})$ reduces to IOWA operator $\text{IOWA}_Q(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{t})$ in Equation (10) of Definition 2.9, where $T = (\mathbf{t}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^2)_{i=1}^n$ with $t_{ij} = t_i$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Furthermore, when $T = (\mathbf{t}_i)_{i=1}^n = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^2)_{i=1}^n$ is with $t_{ij} = x_i$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then the GniOWA operator in (12) $\text{GniOWA}_{\mathbf{w}^\Delta}(\mathbf{x})$ in actual reduces to OWA operator $\text{OWA}_{\mathbf{w}}(\mathbf{x})$ defined by RIM quantifier Q with $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{w}^{(Q)}$ where $\mathbf{w}^{(Q)}$ is the weight vector defined in Definition 2.6.

Example 4.1. Let C_i ($i = 1, 2$) be two criteria under evaluation in terms of one candidate alternative. The expert group consisting of 10 professionals $\{E_k\}$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, 10$) is invited to judge the importance of each criterion based on $\{1$ “very important,” 2 “important,” 3 “less important,” 4 “not important” $\}$. A simple survey is carried out among this group of experts $\{E_k\}$, and each expert E_k reports his/her own opinion about which type of importance the criterion C_i ($i \in \{1, 2\}$) is of. For the criterion C_1 , its opinion vector is represented by an OWA weight vector $\mathbf{t}_1 = (t_{11}, t_{12}, t_{13}, t_{14}) = (0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1)$; and as for the criterion C_2 , its opinion vector is $\mathbf{t}_2 = (t_{21}, t_{22}, t_{23}, t_{24}) = (0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1)$.

Step 1. The accumulation vector of $\mathbf{t}_i = (t_{ij})_{j=1}^4$ ($i \in \{1, 2\}$) are calculated as $\vec{t}_{11} = 0.4, \vec{t}_{12} = 0.6, \vec{t}_{13} = 0.9, \vec{t}_{14} = 1, \vec{t}_{21} = 0.3, \vec{t}_{22} = 0.7, \vec{t}_{23} = 0.9, \vec{t}_{24} = 1$.

Step 2. The cardinalities are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{card}(U(T, 1, 1)) &= 4, & \text{card}(E(T, 1, 1)) &= 1, & \text{card}(L(T, 1, 1)) &= 1; \\ \text{card}(U(T, 1, 2)) &= 3, & \text{card}(E(T, 1, 2)) &= 1, & \text{card}(L(T, 1, 2)) &= 2; \\ \text{card}(U(T, 1, 3)) &= 0, & \text{card}(E(T, 1, 3)) &= 2, & \text{card}(L(T, 1, 3)) &= 4. \end{aligned}$$

By the same token,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{card}(U(T, 2, 1)) &= 5, & \text{card}(E(T, 2, 1)) &= 1, & \text{card}(L(T, 2, 1)) &= 0; \\ \text{card}(U(T, 2, 2)) &= 2, & \text{card}(E(T, 2, 2)) &= 1, & \text{card}(L(T, 2, 2)) &= 3; \\ \text{card}(U(T, 2, 3)) &= 0, & \text{card}(E(T, 2, 3)) &= 2, & \text{card}(L(T, 2, 3)) &= 4. \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. With the obtained cardinalities and Equation (14), we further establish that

$$\begin{aligned} w_1^\Delta &= Q\left(\frac{5}{6}\right) - Q\left(\frac{3}{6}\right) + Q\left(\frac{2}{6}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0}{6}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} = Q\left(\frac{5}{6}\right) - Q\left(\frac{2.5}{6}\right) + \frac{Q\left(\frac{1.8}{6}\right) - Q(0)}{2}, \\ w_2^\Delta &= Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{5}{6}\right) + Q\left(\frac{3}{6}\right) - Q\left(\frac{2}{6}\right) + \frac{Q\left(\frac{2}{6}\right) - Q(0)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that $w_1^\Delta + w_2^\Delta = Q(1) - Q(0) = 1$ and, in the case that $Q(x) = x$, we have $w_1^\Delta = \frac{1}{2}, w_2^\Delta = \frac{1}{2}$.

In Method 1, we only derived an ordering from inductive information or accumulation information, depending on the magnitudes of those entries but without actually expressing them in the corresponding formula. With some difference from Method 1, the following alternative method practically uses the magnitudes of each entry in accumulation information $\vec{T} = ((\vec{t}_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$.

4.2 Weights Allocation Method 2

Entries induced method with using magnitudes from accumulation information.

Steps 1 and 2 are the same as in Method 1. In Step 3, with selected RIM quantifier Q , define weight vector $\mathbf{w}^\Delta = (w_i^\Delta)_{i=1}^n = H(T; Q)$ such that

$$w_i^\Delta = \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \frac{Q\left(1 - \frac{\sum_{(k,s) \in L(T,i,j)} \vec{t}_{ks}}{n \cdot m-1}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\sum_{(k,s) \in U(T,i,j)} \vec{t}_{ks}}{n \cdot m-1}\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \vec{t}_{ij}}. \quad (15)$$

Remark 4.2. In Equation (15), the fact $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i^\Delta = 1$ is not difficult to observe due to the fact that all the unit interval $[0, 1]$ has been appropriately divided into $(m - 1)n$ disjoint intervals which cover $[0, 1]$.

Example 4.2. The implementation of Weights Allocation Method 2 can be demonstrated in the use of the exemplified background as we specified in Example 4.1. In particular, Steps 1 and 2 are exactly the same with those of Example 4.1 and, therefore, we only offer the detailed calculation process of Step 3.

Step 3. It is convenient to calculate that

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^3 \vec{t}_{ij} = (\vec{t}_{11} + \vec{t}_{12} + \vec{t}_{13}) + (\vec{t}_{21} + \vec{t}_{22} + \vec{t}_{23}) = 3.8.$$

On the basis of the results obtained from Steps 1 and 2 having been given in Example 4.1, using (15) derives that

$$\begin{aligned} w_1^\Delta &= Q\left(\frac{3.5}{3.8}\right) - Q\left(\frac{2.5}{3.8}\right) + \frac{Q\left(\frac{1.8}{3.8}\right) - Q(0)}{2}, \\ w_2^\Delta &= Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{3.5}{3.8}\right) + Q\left(\frac{2.5}{3.8}\right) + Q\left(\frac{1.8}{3.8}\right) + \frac{Q\left(\frac{1.8}{3.8}\right) - Q(0)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that $w_1^\Delta + w_2^\Delta = Q(1) - Q(0) = 1$ and, in the case that $Q(x) = x$, we have $w_1^\Delta = w_2^\Delta = \frac{1}{2}$.

5 Weights Allocations in IOWA Operators Induced from the Structures of OWA Weight Vectors

In Section 4, we proposed two related weights allocation methods which actually used the accumulation information $\vec{T} = ((\vec{t}_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$. In this section, we discuss another inductive method which considers the structure of OWA weight vectors by using only inductive information $T = ((t_{ij})_{j=1}^m)_{i=1}^n$ but without involving any accumulation information.

We analyze the principle and reasonability of the different proposed methods. In Weights Allocation Methods 1 and 2, the weights allocations do not depend on the index j in \vec{t}_{ij} . Instead, what matters is the magnitudes of \vec{t}_{ij} ; for example, if $\vec{t}_{13} = \vec{t}_{22}$, then for an optimistic RIM quantifier, such as $Q(t) = t^2$, though $3 > 2$, \vec{t}_{22} will cause equal weight allocated to w_2^Δ to that amount allocated to w_1^Δ caused by \vec{t}_{13} . Differently, the weight allocation mechanism in the following method will be affected by the index j in t_{ij} ; put simply, with the same magnitude of t_{ij} in inductive information, the entry t_{ij} with smaller j will generally be more efficient to carry more weight to w_i^Δ given that the involved RIM quantifier Q is optimistic, and vice versa. This mechanism is reasonable because the smaller j represents its position in linearly ordered set $(\{1, \dots, m\}, \leq)$ is nearer the front;

for example, in the linearly ordered adverbs 1 “very important,” 2 “important,” 3 “less important,” and 4 “not important” as presented previously, smaller index represents more important and hence should have more efficiency to allocate weight when Q is optimistic, and vice versa. Of course, the magnitudes of every t_{ij} will also affect the weight allocation in the following method. The whole principle of the method is in line with the structure of OWA weight vector.

5.1 Weights Allocation Method 3

Entries induced method using only inductive information.

Step 1. For each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, add up $(t_{ij})_{i=1}^n$ and obtain $h_j = \sum_{i=1}^n t_{ij}$; clearly $\sum_{j=1}^m h_j = n$ and $\mathbf{h} = (h_j)_{j=1}^m$ is a vector useful in the remainder of this study.

Step 2. With given RIM quantifier Q and the accumulation vector of \mathbf{h} , $\vec{\mathbf{h}} = (\vec{h}_j)_{j=1}^m$, generate a new weight vector $\mathbf{s} = (s_j)_{j=1}^m$, such that

$$s_j = Q\left(\frac{\vec{h}_j}{n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\vec{h}_{j-1}}{n}\right) \quad (Q\left(\frac{\vec{h}_0}{n}\right) \triangleq 0).$$

Step 3. For each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, allocate a part of s_j to help form w_i^Δ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. If $s_j > 0$, the amount of weight $s_j^{(i)}$ allocated to w_i^Δ from s_j is determined by

$$s_j^{(i)} = \frac{t_{ij}}{n} \cdot s_j = \frac{t_{ij}}{h_j} \cdot s_j \quad (i \in \{1, \dots, n\});$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^m t_{kj}$$

if $h_j = 0$, define $s_j^{(i)} = 0$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$).

Step 4. For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, sum up $s_j^{(i)}$ in terms of j taken over $\{1, \dots, m\}$ to obtain w_i^Δ :

$$w_i^\Delta = \sum_{j=1}^m s_j^{(i)}.$$

Example 5.1. We continue to use the data source as being established in Example 4.1. The following steps are established to determine the weights of C_i ($i = 1, 2$) in the use of Weights Allocation Method 3.

Step 1. By adding up $(t_{ij})_{i=1}^2$, we obtain the OWA weight vector $\mathbf{h} = (h_j)_{j=1}^4$ in which $h_1 = 0.7$, $h_2 = 0.6$, $h_3 = 0.5$, $h_4 = 0.2$.

Step 2. The accumulation vector of \mathbf{h} is $\vec{h}_1 = 0.7$, $\vec{h}_2 = 1.3$, $\vec{h}_3 = 1.8$, $\vec{h}_4 = 2.0$. Then,

the new weight vector $\mathbf{s} = (s_j)_{j=1}^4$ is further calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &= Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right) - Q(0) = Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right), \\ s_2 &= Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right), \\ s_3 &= Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right), \\ s_4 &= Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. The amounts $s_j^{(i)}$ ($i = 1, 2; j = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are:

$$\begin{aligned} s_1^{(1)} &= \frac{0.4}{0.7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right) = \frac{4}{7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right), & s_1^{(2)} &= \frac{0.3}{0.7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right) = \frac{3}{7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right), \\ s_2^{(1)} &= \frac{0.2}{0.6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{2}{6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right), & s_2^{(2)} &= \frac{0.4}{0.6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{4}{6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right), \\ s_3^{(1)} &= \frac{0.3}{0.5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{3}{5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right), & s_3^{(2)} &= \frac{0.2}{0.5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{2}{5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right), \\ s_4^{(1)} &= \frac{0.1}{0.2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{1}{2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right), & s_4^{(2)} &= \frac{0.1}{0.2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right) = \frac{1}{2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right). \end{aligned}$$

Step 4. Eventually, the weights of the two criteria w_i^Δ ($i = 1, 2$) can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} w_1^\Delta &= \sum_{j=1}^4 s_j^{(1)} = \frac{4}{7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{3}{5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{1}{2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right), \\ w_2^\Delta &= \sum_{j=1}^4 s_j^{(2)} = \frac{3}{7}Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right) + \frac{4}{6}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{0.7}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{2}{5}\left(Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right) - Q\left(\frac{1.3}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{1}{2}\left(Q(1) - Q\left(\frac{1.8}{2}\right)\right). \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that $w_1^\Delta + w_2^\Delta = Q(1) - Q(0) = 1$ and, in the case that $Q(x) = x$, we have $w_1^\Delta = w_2^\Delta = \frac{1}{2}$.

6 Some Properties of the Three Weights Inductive Methods Using Convex/Concave RIM Quantifiers

Convex (and concave) RIM quantifiers are with particular importance in preference-involved decision making and have some good properties [34]. Recall that an RIM quantifier $Q: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is *convex* if for any $a, b \in [0, 1]$ and any $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$Q(\lambda a + (1 - \lambda)b) \leq \lambda Q(a) + (1 - \lambda)Q(b). \quad (16)$$

Convex RIM quantifiers embody the Strictly Pessimistic Preference [34]. Dually, we call an RIM quantifier Q *concave*, if for any $a, b \in [0, 1]$ and any $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$Q(\lambda a + (1 - \lambda)b) \geq \lambda Q(a) + (1 - \lambda)Q(b). \quad (17)$$

Concave RIM quantifiers embody the Strictly Optimistic Preference [34]. We also have that if an RIM quantifier Q is convex, then $\text{orness}(Q) = \int_0^1 Q(\lambda) d\lambda \leq \int_0^1 \lambda d\lambda = 0.5$; conversely, if an RIM quantifier Q is concave, then $\text{orness}(Q) \geq 0.5$.

With using convex/concave RIM quantifiers, in what follows we analyze some basic properties, such as monotonicities revolving around the three weights allocation methods introduced previously.

Proposition 6.1. *In Weights Allocation Methods 1–3, for any RIM quantifier Q , if $\mathbf{t}_a = \mathbf{t}_b$ (i.e., $t_{aj} = t_{bj}$, $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$) with $a, b \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then $w_a^\Delta = w_b^\Delta$.*

The following property is direct from the respective weights allocation procedure and its trivial proof is omitted.

Lemma 6.1 ([34]). *If $Q: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is convex, then for any $a_1, a_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $d \in [0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq a_1 \leq a_2$ and $a_1 + d, a_2 + d \leq 1$, we have*

$$Q(a_1 + d) - Q(a_1) \leq Q(a_2 + d) - Q(a_2). \quad (18)$$

Lemma 6.2. *For any $a, b, c \in [0, 1]$ with $a < b < c$,*

(i) *if Q is any convex RIM quantifier, then*

$$\frac{Q(b) - Q(a)}{b - a} \leq \frac{Q(c) - Q(a)}{c - a} \leq \frac{Q(c) - Q(b)}{c - b}; \quad (19)$$

(ii) *if Q is any concave RIM quantifier, then the inequalities in (19) are reversed:*

$$\frac{Q(b) - Q(a)}{b - a} \geq \frac{Q(c) - Q(a)}{c - a} \geq \frac{Q(c) - Q(b)}{c - b}. \quad (20)$$

Lemma 6.3. *For any $a, b, c, d \in [0, 1]$ with $a < b \leq c < d$,*

(i) *if Q is any convex RIM quantifier, then*

$$\frac{Q(b) - Q(a)}{b - a} \leq \frac{Q(d) - Q(c)}{d - c}; \quad (21)$$

(ii) *if Q is any concave RIM quantifier, then the inequality in (21) is reversed:*

$$\frac{Q(b) - Q(a)}{b - a} \geq \frac{Q(d) - Q(c)}{d - c}. \quad (22)$$

Proposition 6.2. *In Weights Allocation Method 1, for any convex (concave) RIM quantifier Q , if $\mathbf{t}_a \preceq \mathbf{t}_b$ (i.e., $\vec{t}_{aj} \leq \vec{t}_{bj}$, for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$) with $a, b \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then $w_a^\Delta \geq w_b^\Delta$ ($w_a^\Delta \leq w_b^\Delta$).*

Proof. By duality, we only consider the case of convex RIM quantifier Q . For each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, since $\vec{t}_{aj} \leq \vec{t}_{bj}$, then clearly $\text{card}(U(T, a, j)) \geq (m-1)n - \text{card}(L(T, b, j))$. Hence,

$$\frac{\text{card}(U(T, a, j))}{(m-1)n} \geq 1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, b, j))}{(m-1)n}.$$

Observe that

$$\frac{\text{card}(E(T, a, j))}{[(m-1)n - \text{card}(L(T, a, j))] - \text{card}(U(T, a, j))} = \frac{\text{card}(E(T, b, j))}{[(m-1)n - \text{card}(L(T, b, j))] - \text{card}(U(T, b, j))} = 1,$$

or equivalently,

$$\frac{\text{card}(E(T, a, j))}{\left[1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, a, j))}{(m-1)n}\right] - \frac{\text{card}(U(T, a, j))}{(m-1)n}} = \frac{\text{card}(E(T, b, j))}{\left[1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, b, j))}{(m-1)n}\right] - \frac{\text{card}(U(T, b, j))}{(m-1)n}}.$$

Then, by Lemma 6.3, we have

$$\frac{Q\left(1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, a, j))}{(m-1)n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\text{card}(U(T, a, j))}{(m-1)n}\right)}{\text{card}(E(T, a, j))} \geq \frac{Q\left(1 - \frac{\text{card}(L(T, b, j))}{(m-1)n}\right) - Q\left(\frac{\text{card}(U(T, b, j))}{(m-1)n}\right)}{\text{card}(E(T, b, j))}.$$

Therefore, directly by Equation (14), we have $w_a^\Delta \geq w_b^\Delta$. \square

Remark 6.1. The similar result cannot be obtained for Weights Allocation Method 2, because in that case it also considers the magnitudes of \vec{t}_{ij} themselves.

Proposition 6.3. *In Weights Allocation Method 3, for any convex (concave) RIM quantifier Q , if $\mathbf{t}_a \preceq \mathbf{t}_b$ (i.e., $\vec{t}_{aj} \leq \vec{t}_{bj}$, for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$) with $a, b \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then $w_a^\Delta \geq w_b^\Delta$ ($w_a^\Delta \leq w_b^\Delta$).*

Proof. By duality, we only consider the case of concave RIM quantifier Q . With denotation $h_j = \sum_{i=1}^n t_{ij}$, by Lemma 6.3 we have

$$\frac{ns_j}{h_j} = \frac{nQ(\vec{h}_j/n) - nQ(\vec{h}_{j-1}/n)}{h_j} \geq \frac{nQ(\vec{h}_{j+1}/n) - nQ(\vec{h}_j/n)}{h_{j+1}} = \frac{ns_{j+1}}{h_{j+1}}$$

for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that $h_j \neq 0$.

Since it is impossible that $h_j = 0$ holds for all $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, then we define $M = \text{card}\{p \in \{1, \dots, m\} : h_p \neq 0\}$. Define an injective mapping $g: \{1, \dots, M\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that (i) $h_{g(k)} \neq 0$ for all $k \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, and (ii) $g(k) < g(k+1)$ for all $k \in \{1, \dots, M-1\}$.

Then, $s_j^{(a)} = \frac{t_{aj}}{h_j} s_j$, and hence

$$w_a^\Delta = \sum_{j=1}^m s_j^{(a)} = \sum_{k=1}^M t_{a-g(k)} \cdot \frac{s_{g(k)}}{h_{g(k)}} = \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{r=1}^k t_{a-g(r)} \cdot \left[\frac{s_{g(k)}}{h_{g(k)}} - \frac{s_{g(k+1)}}{h_{g(k+1)}} \right] = \sum_{k=1}^M \vec{t}_{a-g(k)} \cdot \left[\frac{s_{g(k)}}{h_{g(k)}} - \frac{s_{g(k+1)}}{h_{g(k+1)}} \right]$$

with $\frac{s_{g(M+1)}}{h_{g(M+1)}} \triangleq 0$. Similarly, we have

$$w_b^\Delta = \sum_{k=1}^M \vec{t}_{b-g(k)} \cdot \left[\frac{s_{g(k)}}{h_{g(k)}} - \frac{s_{g(k+1)}}{h_{g(k+1)}} \right].$$

Since $\vec{t}_{a_j} \leq \vec{t}_{b_j}$ for each $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, then $\vec{t}_{a-g(k)} \leq \vec{t}_{b-g(k)}$ for each $k \in \{1, \dots, M\}$. Consequently, we obtain $w_a^\Delta \leq w_b^\Delta$. \square

7 Conclusions

The development and enrichment of aggregation operators can provide more choices to automated evaluation and can add new contents to computational intelligence. This study extended and generalized the IOWA operators, which were based on real-number-based inductive information. The proposed methods considered a more general situation in which the inductive information is OWA weight vectors rather than real numbers. As such we proposed the standard form of GnIOWA operator. We showed the usefulness and importance of GnIOWA in decision-making and evaluation practices.

This study proposed three different weights allocation mechanisms for GnIOWA operators. The first one only considered the derived ordering from the accumulation of OWA weight vectors, while the second one also took into account the magnitudes of the accumulation of OWA weight vectors. Therefore, when the involved RIM quantifier Q is convex/concave, we further proved that a type of monotonicity holds for the first method, but it does not hold for the second one.

The third method did not use the accumulation of OWA weight vector, but instead it directly allocated weights in accordance with the priorities in positions of the entries in the OWA weight vectors. With clear and succinct analyses, we proved that the third method holds for the monotonicity given that the involved RIM quantifier Q is convex/concave.

Apart from the contribution in the theory of aggregation operators, this study is also practical in decision making since it provided some reasonable approaches to handle the induced aggregation where the inducing variable is OWA weight vectors rather than real values. The proposed methods also have some limitations. For example, it cannot be directly applied in linguistic decision making. Therefore, in further study, we will conduct the corresponding study in induced aggregation with linguistic decision-making environment. In addition, in aggregation theory this study can also be further extended into the setting where the inducing variable becomes fuzzy measures which generalize OWA weight vectors.

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References

- [1] Grabisch M, Marichal J-L, Mesiar R, Pap E. *Aggregation Functions*. Vol. 127. New York: Cambridge University Press; 2009.
- [2] Jin L, Mesiar R, Borkotokey S, Kalina M. Certainty aggregation and the certainty fuzzy measures. *Int J Intell Syst*. 2018;33:759–770.
- [3] Torra V, Narukawa Y. The interpretation of fuzzy integrals and their application to fuzzy systems. *Int J Approx Reason*. 2006;41:43–58.
- [4] Mesiar R, Borkotokey S, Jin L, Kalina M. Aggregation under uncertainty. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2018;26:2475–2478.
- [5] Paternain D, De Miguel L, Ochoa G, Lizasoain I, Mesiar R, Bustince H. The interval-valued Choquet integral based on admissible permutations. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2018;27(8):1638–1647.
- [6] Jin L. Vector t-norms with applications. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2016;25:1644–1654.
- [7] Jin L, Mesiar R. The metric space of ordered weighted average operators with distance based on accumulated entries. *Int J Intell Syst*. 2017;32:665–675.
- [8] Jin L, Mesiar R, Yager RR. Melting probability measure with OWA operator to generate fuzzy measure: the crescent method. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2018;27:1309–1316.
- [9] Jin L, Mesiar R, Yager R, Qin J. Dynamic weights allocation according to uncertain evaluation information. *Int J Gen Syst*. 2019;48:33–47.
- [10] Klement EP, Mesiar R. Discrete integrals and axiomatically defined functionals. *Axioms*. 2012;1:9–20.
- [11] Klement EP, Mesiar R, Pap E. A universal integral as common frame for Choquet and Sugeno integral. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2009;18:178–187.
- [12] Liu X, Da Q. A decision tree solution considering the decision maker's attitude. *Fuzzy Sets Syst*. 2005;152:437–454.

- [13] Mesiar R, Stupňanová A, Yager RR. Generalizations of OWA operators. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst.* 2015;23:2154–2162.
- [14] Ouyang Y. Improved minimax disparity model for obtaining OWA operator weights: issue of multiple solutions. *Inf Sci.* 2015;320:101–106.
- [15] Torra V. The weighted OWA operator. *Int J Intell Syst.* 1997;12:153–166.
- [16] Yager RR, Kacprzyk J, Beliakov G. *Recent Developments in the Ordered Weighted Averaging Operators: Theory and Practice*. Vol. 265. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer; 2011.
- [17] Wei G, Gao H, Wei Y. Some q-rung orthopair fuzzy Heronian mean operators in multiple attribute decision making. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2018;33:1426–1458.
- [18] Liu Z, Li L, Li J. q-Rung orthopair uncertain linguistic partitioned Bonferroni mean operators and its application to multiple attribute decision-making method. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2019;34:2490–2520.
- [19] Liu H-C, Quan M-Y, Shi H, Guo C. An integrated MCDM method for robot selection under interval-valued Pythagorean uncertain linguistic environment. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2019;34:188–214.
- [20] Lin M, Li X, Chen L. Linguistic q-rung orthopair fuzzy sets and their interactional partitioned Heronian mean aggregation operators. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2020;35:217–249.
- [21] Ding X-F, Liu H-C. A new approach for emergency decision-making based on zero-sum game with Pythagorean fuzzy uncertain linguistic variables. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2019;34:1667–1684.
- [22] Gong J-W, Li Q, Yin L, Liu H-C. Undergraduate teaching audit and evaluation using an extended MABAC method under q-rung orthopair fuzzy environment. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2020;35:1912–1933.
- [23] Lin M, Xu W, Lin Z, Chen R. Determine OWA operator weights using kernel density estimation. *Econ Res—Ekonom Istraž.* 2020;33:1441–1464.
- [24] Yager RR. On ordered weighted averaging aggregation operators in multicriteria decisionmaking. *IEEE Trans Syst Man Cybern.* 1988;18:183–190.
- [25] Yager RR. Induced aggregation operators. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 2003;137:59–69.
- [26] Yager RR, Filev DP. Induced ordered weighted averaging operators. *IEEE Trans Syst Man Cybern Part B (Cybern).* 1999;29:141–150.
- [27] Choquet G. Theory of capacities. *Ann l'institut Fourier.* 1954;5:131–295.

- [28] Sugeno M. *Theory of Fuzzy Integrals and its Applications* (Doctor Thesis). Tokyo Institute of Technology; 1974.
- [29] Shilkret N. Maxitive measure and integration. *Indagationes Mathematicae*. 1971;74:109–116.
- [30] Chen Z-S, Yu C, Chin K-S, Martínez L. An enhanced ordered weighted averaging operators generation algorithm with applications for multicriteria decision making. *Appl Math Modelling*. 2019;71:467–490.
- [31] Pu X, Jin L, Mesiar R, Yager RR. Continuous parameterized families of rim quantifiers and quasi-preference with some properties. *Inf Sci*. 2019;481:24–32.
- [32] Yager RR. Quantifier guided aggregation using OWA operators. *Int J Intell Syst*. 1996;11:49–73.
- [33] Liu X. On the properties of equidifferent rim quantifier with generating function. *Int J Gen Syst*. 2005;34:579–594.
- [34] Jin L, Mesiar R, Yager R. Ordered weighted averaging aggregation on convex poset. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst*. 2019;27:612–617.